

A Comparative Study of VoIP Protocols

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Abstract— Nowadays, Multimedia Communication has been developed and improved rapidly in order to enable users to communicate between each other over the Internet. In general, the multimedia communication consists of audio, video and instant messages communication. This paper surveys the functions and the privileges of different voice over Internet protocols (VoIP), such as InterAsterisk eXchange Protocol (IAX), Session Initiation Protocol (SIP), and H.323 protocol. As well as, this paper will make some comparisons among them in terms of signaling messages, codec's, transport protocols, and media transport, etc.

Keywords- *Multimedia; VoIP; InterAsterisk eXchange Protocol (IAX); Session Initiation Protocol (SIP); H.323 protocol; Signaling Messages*

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last few years, the needs to provide the communication facilities among participants everywhere and every time via computer network systems have been increased. These network systems enable the use of multimedia applications with many kinds of media data, such as audio, video, graphics, images, and text. This rapid expansion and potential underlies the significance of the interworking. Multimedia technology promises to make smooth and very effective interactions among people in different geographical areas [18]. However, the provided multimedia services must be improved.

In recent years, Voice over IP (VoIP) technologies [15] has been developed and many significant progresses have been done in research and commercially. VoIP allows many users to make VoIP phone calls instead of the Public Switched Telephone Network (PSTN) through such technologies as InterAsterisk eXchange Protocol (IAX) [1][5], Session Initiation Protocol (SIP) [12], and H.323 protocol [25][26]. VoIP can offer a higher quality and yet more reasonable phone service than PSTN. The telecommunication industry is going towards using VoIP as their main phone infrastructure [15]. VoIP services become so popular in the last few years because it is inexpensive compared to the traditional telephony. VoIP can be integrated with other services, such as video conferences, instant messages and presence services.

Several signaling protocols and techniques are used to help bridging the gap between the endpoints, such as H.323 Protocol, SIP protocol [16], IAX protocol, etc. These protocols provide video, audio, and data communication among participants [17]. In order to provide media transfer between participants, the signaling messages of each protocol are discussed in this paper.

This paper is organized into 4 sections; **II** briefly describes the privileges of VoIP protocols and compares among their own signals. **III** is the first comparison of VoIP protocols in term of media codec's. **IV** is the second comparison of VoIP protocols in terms of transport protocols, media transport, and others. And **V** is a summary of this paper and our planned future research.

II. VOIP PROTOCOLS

A. Session Initiation Protocol (SIP)

SIP is an application-layer control protocol [11] that can establish, modify, and terminate multimedia sessions (conferences) such as Internet telephony calls [9][14][25][26][27]. SIP can also invite participants to already existing sessions, such as multicast conferences. Media can be added to (and removed from) an existing session. SIP transparently supports name mapping and redirection services, which supports personal mobility-users can maintain a single externally visible identifier regardless of their network location [12][13]. SIP protocol enables Internet endpoints (called user agents) to discover one another and to agree on a characterization of a session they would like to share. For locating prospective session participants, and for other functions, SIP enables the creation of an infrastructure of network hosts (called proxy servers) to which user agents can send registrations, invitations to sessions, and other requests. SIP is an agile, general-purpose tool for creating, modifying, and terminating sessions that works independently of underlying transport protocols and without dependency on the type of session that is being established [19][20][22][23][28].

SIP does not carry any voice or video data itself. It merely allows two endpoints to set up connection to transfer

that traffic between each other via Real-time Transport Protocol (RTP) [3][15]. The User Datagram Protocol (UDP) and Transport Control Protocol (TCP) [2] are transport protocols used to transfer audio and video data [4]. SIP protocol has many features such as the service of text-based which allows easy implementation in object oriented programming languages, flexibility, extensibility, less signaling, transport layer-protocol neutral and parallel search [22][23][24]. SIP uses many signaling messages in order to handle the communication between two nodes or more. Figure 1 shows the SIP call setup between two nodes.

Figure 1. Call Setup with SIP [10]

SIP makes use of the six request methods: INVITE, ACK, OPTIONS, BYE, CANCEL and REGISTER in order to control the registration, call setup, and call teardown [25]. Table I describes the request messages in details.

TABLE I. SIP REQUEST METHODS [25]

SIP Request Messages	Usage
INVITE	To invite a user to participate in a multimedia session
ACK	To confirm that the final response has received
OPTIONS	To query the server capabilities.
BYE	To leave the call session
CANCEL	To abort a previous request
REGISTER	To inform the registrar of the client's current location

SIP requests are followed by one or more SIP responses, which are classified into six categories [25]. Table II shows the SIP response messages.

TABLE II. SIP RESPONSE METHODS [25]

SIP Response Messages	Usage
1xx Informational	Request received, continuing to process request
2xx Success	The action was successfully received
3xx Redirection	Further action must be taken to complete the request
4xx Client Error	The request contains bad syntax or cannot be fulfilled at this server
5xx Server Error	The request cannot be fulfilled at this server because of server error
6xx Global Failure	The request is invalid at any server

B. InterAsterisk eXchange Protocol (IAX)

In (2004) Mark Spencer [5] has created the Inter-Asterisk eXchange (IAX) protocol for asterisk that performs VoIP signaling [6][7]. Streaming media is managed, controlled and transmitted through the Internet Protocol (IP) networks based on this protocol. Any type of streaming media could be used by this protocol. However, IP voice calls are basically being controlled by IAX protocol [14]. Furthermore, this protocol can be called as a peer to peer (P2P) protocol that performs two types of connections which are Voice over IP (VoIP) connections through the servers and Client-Server communication. IAX is currently changed to IAX2 which is the second version of the IAX protocol. The IAX2 has deprecated the original IAX protocol [5]. Call signaling and multimedia transport functions are supported by the IAX protocol. In the same session and by using IAX, Voice streams (multimedia and signaling) are conveyed. Furthermore, IAX supports the trunk connections concept for numerous calls. The bandwidth usage is reduced when this concept is being used because all the protocol overhead is shared for all the calls between two IAX nodes. Over a single link, IAX provides multiplexing channels [11].

IAX is a simple protocol in such a way Network Address Translation (NAT) traversal complications are avoided by it [8]. The Mini and Full frames are sent between two endpoints A and B. Each audio/video flow is of IAX Mini

Frames (M frames) which contains 4 byte header. The flow is supplemented by periodic Full Frames (F Frames) includes synchronization information. User Datagram Protocol (UDP) is a transport protocol used by IAX to transfer audio and video data [4]. Figure 2 shows the ongoing call between two IAX endpoints.

Figure 2. IAX Communication [7]

IAX uses several signals (i.e. NEW, RINGING, ANSWER, HANGUP, etc) in order to setup or teardown the call between two clients [8]. Table III explains the functions of IAX signaling methods.

TABLE III. IAX SIGNALING MESSAGES [8]

IAX Signals	Usage
NEW	To place calls
AUTHREQ	To authenticate
ACCEPT	To accept call leg
PROCEEDING	Proceed to join
RINGING	Ring at destination
ANSWER	In Call
ACK	Acknowledgment
HANGUP	To end the call

C. H.323 Protocol

H.323 is an umbrella standard that provides well-defined system architecture [10], and implementation guidelines that cover call set-up, call control, and the media used in the call [24][25][26]. It was established by the International Telecommunications Union (ITU) as the first communications protocol for real time multimedia communication over IP. H.323 takes the more telecommunications-oriented approach to voice/video over IP. H.323 protocol provides a comparable functionality using different mechanisms and offers highly network management and interoperability [21][27].

H.323 protocol uses either TCP or UDP to transmit the audio/video packet to the destination side. As well as, Real time Transport protocol (RTP) is used to carry the media packets via Internet. Figure 3 Shows how does H.323 set up the call between to nodes.

Figure 3. Call Setup with H.323 [10]

H.323 protocol has many signals used to manage and control the call, such as ARQ, ACF, ALERT, etc. Some of these messages are used to confirm, reject, and request the messages [29]. Table IV illustrates the H.323 signals.

TABLE IV. H.323 SIGNALING MESSAGES [29]

H.323 Signals	Usage
Setup	To initially request that a call is set up
Call Proceeding	To indicate that the call has is currently being processed by the called terminal
Alert	The called terminal is ringing

ARQ	Admission request
Connect	The two-way communication is ready to commence
Reject	A rejection message is sent and call setup is halted.
Release Complete	An indication that the sender wishes to end the call
ACF	Admission Confirm Message

III. THE CODEC'S USED IN VOIP PROTOCOLS

In this section, we will compare between IAX, SIP, and H.323 in terms of codec's used for each of them [7][30]. Table V shows the comparison of the three VoIP protocols.

TABLE V. MEDIA CODEC'S OF IAX, SIP, AND H.323

	IAX	SIP	H.323
G.711	√	√	√
G.721	√	×	×
G.722	√	√	√
G.723	√	√	√
G.726	√	×	√
G.728	×	√	√
G.729	√	√	√
GSM	√	√	×
Speex	√	√	√
iLBC	√	√	×
ACC	×	√	√
AAL2	√	×	×
IMA ADPCM	√	×	×
LPC10	√	×	×
T.140	×	×	√
H.261	×	×	√
H.263	×	√	√
H.264	√	√	√

IV. TRANSPORT PROTOCOLS, MEDIA TRANSPORT, SERVER NEEDED, IP PORTS, CALL SETUP SIGNALS, AND HEADERS USED IN VOIP PROTOCOLS

In this section, we will do another comparison of IAX, SIP, and H.323 in terms of transport protocol, media transport, call setup signals, etc [1][30]. Table VI shows the comparison of the three VoIP protocols.

TABLE VI. A COMPARISON AMONG IAX, SIP, AND H.323

	IAX	SIP	H.323
Transport Protocol	UDP	TCP, UDP	TCP, UDP
Media Transport	Full/Mini Frames	RTP/RTCP, SRTP	RTP/RTCP, SRTP
Server Needed	Peer to peer	Proxy Server	Gatekeeper
IP Port for TCP/UDP	4569	5060	3230-3253 5001 5004-6004
Call Setup	New→ ←Accept Ack→	Invite→ ←200Ok Ack→	Setup→ ←Connect Ack→
Header Used	Full/Mini Headers	RTP Header	RTP Header

V. CONCLUSION

This paper surveys the functions and the privileges of different VoIP protocols (i.e. IAX, SIP, and H.323). In this paper, we made some comparisons of these protocols in terms of request/response signals, media codec's used, transport protocols, media transport, etc. We can observe that each protocol has its own privileges that differ from the others. In the future, we will do another comparison in terms of quality of services (packet delay, packet loss, jitter, and packet reordering), bandwidth consumption, services, extensibility, scalability, etc.

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